

Humorous content effectiveness in marine biotoxins' risk communication through social media

Panagiota Katikou^{1,2*}, Gideon Mekonnen Jonathan², Brian Kloss³

¹Directorate of Research, Innovation and Education, Ministry of Rural Development and Food, 54626 Thessaloniki, Greece; ²Department of Computer and Systems Sciences (DSV), Stockholm University, Postbox 7003, SE-16407 Kista, Sweden; ³SUNY Upstate Medical University, 550 East Genesee Street, Syracuse, NY 13202, U.S.A.

*corresponding author's email: pkatikou@otenet.gr

Abstract

Social media are largely integrated into citizens' daily routines and constitute powerful communication tools, often exploited by regulatory authorities as information distribution channels for risk communication purposes. Food safety issues frequently raise public concern, requiring management through trustworthy information provision, ideally disseminated by digital means. Risk communication strategies entailing the use of humor in social media are increasingly becoming popular, aiming to raise public awareness and induce risk perception. The objective of this work was to assess the effectiveness of humor-mediated risk communication strategies regarding the food safety hazard of marine biotoxins in a multinational audience. A multinational survey targeting adult English-speaking social media users was conducted, also involving participants with food safety and marine biotoxin expertise, by means of an online questionnaire that included: (a) demographical data, educational/professional background, food safety-related attitude and social media usage; and (b) respondents' perception on various effectiveness parameters, examining three groups of materials relevant to marine biotoxins (conventional, humorous and combination), as risk communication scenarios. The majority of the 218 participants indicated humorous materials as of lower effectiveness than conventional ones; however, the former were scored as more "likeable" or sharable, especially by those more familiar with food safety and/or marine biotoxins. Interestingly, participants perceived materials combining both humorous and conventional elements as comparably effective to those purely conventional. In conclusion, materials combining both informative and humorous elements, may constitute potentially valuable tools in food safety/marine biotoxins' risk communication through social media, by further content optimization.

Keywords: humor, marine biotoxins, risk communication, social media, user perception

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Introduction

Social media (SM) are popular and easily accessible communication tools, globally constituting a part in peoples' daily routines, due to their low usage costs and user friendliness (Charlebois and Summan, 2015). Exploitation of SM covers a wide range of purposes, from plain entertainment and social networking, to distance education, scientific information dissemination, risk communication (RC) and professional interactions (Kuttschreuter *et al.*, 2014). As such, regulatory bodies and public administration organizations pursue an active presence in multiple SM, with official accounts serving as valuable distribution channels for information of both utmost significance and simple interest to citizens/consumers (Charlebois and Summan, 2015; Ruzza *et al.*, 2020). Of particular importance are RC activities related to food safety (FS), public health and environment/climate change, nowadays comprising popular topics of citizen/consumer concern, frequently generating online debates (Rutsaert *et al.*, 2013; Mou and Lin, 2014; Kuttschreuter *et al.*, 2014; Overbey *et al.*, 2017; Skurka *et al.*, 2018; Meadows *et al.*, 2019; Topp *et al.*, 2019).

Strategies involving SM networks entail dissemination of messages specifically tailored to evoke emotions, such as amusement, fear, concern, and frustration, aiming at capitalizing the audiences' appeal to induce risk perception. Emotional responses may influence individuals' potential towards undertaking preventive actions, or even evoke crises' escalation. Humorous/sarcastic messages in SM seem to be the most popular with high like-and-share rates (Mou and Lin, 2014; Overbey *et al.*, 2017; Skurka *et al.*,

2018; Meadows *et al.*, 2019). In this context, RC-responsible agencies progressively use humorous material to induce positive emotions, such as amusement and relief, even in severe public health crises (Chew and Eysenbach, 2010; Fraustino and Ma, 2015; Meadows *et al.*, 2019; Karmegam and Mapillairaju, 2020).

Marine biotoxins (MBs) were chosen as a food-safety theme for the humorous content, being tightly connected with both public health (as causes of human illness), and environmental/ climate change influences (as products of toxic microalgae during proliferations known as harmful algal blooms) (Morabito *et al.*, 2017), thus fitting within all major thematic areas considered in the literature comprising the study's theoretical framework. As such, the aim of this study was to explore the effectiveness of humor-mediated risk communication strategies considering the food safety hazard of marine biotoxins, at a multinational level. To serve this aim, the following research questions (RQ) were formed: RQ1: To what extent is humorous content on social media perceived as effective in communicating risks related to marine biotoxins? RQ2: To what extent is this perceived effectiveness associated with participants' demographic characteristics, level of previous familiarization/expert knowledge, and personal attitudes on FS issues?

Material and Methods

Research strategy and data collection method
A survey strategy was chosen to obtain primary, factual empirical data, delivered by

an adequately large sample of the targeted population. Addressing a diverse multinational audience at a specific time-point by means of quantifiable rigid questions, in a low-cost way, indicated “questionnaire” as the optimal data collection method (Denscombe, 2010).

A web-based questionnaire qualified as an ideal choice, taking into account time and resources constraints, design attractiveness (graphics and audio-visual material), and user-friendliness of web-hosted applications, dissemination easiness and automated transfer of responses to specifically generated spreadsheets (Denscombe, 2010; Johannesson and Perjons, 2014).

Questionnaire properties and content

The questionnaire accommodated the literacy level of adult English-speaking participants without any prior experience on either FS or MB risks, with technical jargon kept to a minimum. All questions were of closed or 5-point Likert-scale type to facilitate quick answering. Three MB scenarios were created (Type-A: conventional, B: humorous, and C: combination), comparable to analogous studies on climate change (Skurka *et al.*, 2018; Topp *et al.*, 2020), but closely fitting our conceptual framework and RQs. The questionnaire was divided into three sections: a) introduction (context, purpose, structure, participation requirements and information on confidentiality and anonymity within the survey; b) main part containing the questions and c) final part (“tick box” statements, in lieu of an ‘informed consent form’). The main part contained 18 questions (Q): Q1-4 enquired on demographics (countries of birth and residence, age and gender), Q5-9 referred to participants’ academic and professional backgrounds and affinity with the FS and

MB sectors; Q10-11 explored respondents’ personal attitudes towards FS issues and Q12-18 examined the participants’ SM use and perception on specific types of MB-related SM contents in fictional cases related to RC purposes. The questionnaire was created using “Google Forms” (Google LLC, Mountain View, CA, U.S.A.).

Sampling – survey participants

Purposive, snowball and convenience sampling (Denscombe, 2010) were combined to attract the widest possible audience at multinational level (both MB and FS experts and general public). The targeted survey participants were English-speaking adults being regular SM users of any professional/educational background.

Data analysis methods

Our study entailed exclusively quantitative data; all variables were discrete, belonging to the nominal or ordinal type. Initially, raw data were cleansed, grouped, and encoded and non-numerical values were replaced by positive integers. Finally, cleansed data were analyzed by the “Statistical Package for Social Sciences” (SPSS) v.27 software, using nonparametric descriptive statistics (median, frequency distribution), graphical exploratory analysis, Kruskal-Wallis H-test, Pearson’s chi-square test, and Spearman’s correlation, at the 95% significance level ($p < 0.05$).

Results and Discussion

A total of 218 responses were collected, corresponding to a calculated error of margin 6.64% at a 95% confidence level, assuming a population from 500 to 700 million English-speaking adult SM users.

1. Demographics – Academic/Professional background. Participants originated from and resided in 34 and 32 different countries/territories, respectively. Different age groups contributed from 1.4% (75 years or older) to 30.7% (45-54 years). Out of 218 responders, 126 (57.8%) were females, whereas 95 of the participants (43.6%) had completed doctorate studies. More than half of the responders were employed in the public sector (119, 54.6%), whereas 62 (28.5%) were private-sector employees or freelancers and 25 (11.5%) were full-time students. People with medical or applied sciences background constituted 63.7% of the sample, with the remaining divided between ICT/Social Sciences (17.0%) and other disciplines (19.3%). Familiarization/experience concerning food safety issues ranged between 11.0 - 31.7%. As regards familiarization with the term “marine biotoxins”, respondents were rather evenly distributed among the five levels, from people who had never encountered the term to field experts, with percentages ranging from 14.2% to 24.8%.

2. Personal attitudes towards food safety and social media use. The majority of participants were generally well aware and interested in FS issues at a proportion of at least 74.3%. Similarly, 62.4% of the respondents expressed concern about the possibility of being affected by a FS incident or crisis. On the other hand, those not interested or aware and those non-concerned about FS constituted minorities of 8.2% and 11%, respectively, indicating a generally positive attitude of participants towards FS importance.

Most responders were multiple SM users; the most popular was Facebook (180 cases, 82.6%), followed by YouTube (165 cases,

75.7%). More than half of the participants also used WhatsApp (56.0%), LinkedIn (52.3%), and Instagram (51.4%), while TikTok showed the lowest penetration with only 6.0% (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Social media used by survey participants.

3. Participants' evaluation of different SM content types. Type-A content (conventional) was perceived by participants as the most informative, credible and alerting (87.1%, 78.4% and 56.9%, respectively), compared to Type-B (humorous; 66.5%, 39.0% and 51.8%, respectively) and Type-C (combination; 77.1%, 64.3% and 55.1%, respectively). On the other hand, 47.2% of the participants considered Type B content as the most amusing/relieving, in contrast to 15.6% and 35.8% for Type-A and C, respectively. Type-C was regarded as the most motivating/creating an intention for action (50.9%), followed by Type-B (47.3%) and Type-A (42.2%) contents.

Concerning the three content types' acceptability, answers exhibiting a positive attitude (Likert scale 4 and 5) cumulatively showed that Type-A and C contents were equally likely to be “liked” (56.0%), with this likelihood being slightly lower for Type-B content (52.3%). Sharing/retweeting likelihood was the highest for Type-A content (58.3%); Types B and C followed closely, with almost half of the participants (49.6% and 50.0%, respectively) also indicating

sharing as possible. Overall though, Type-A content was perceived as the most effective RC means by 78.0% of the participants, with Types C and B accounting for 71.1% and 65.6%, respectively.

Kruskal-Wallis H-testing indicated a significant difference ($p < 0.05$) between distributions of the three content types regarding their potential for creating awareness, trust, and sense of relief, as well as their perceived effectiveness. Pair-wise comparisons showed that humorous content (Type-B) was considered as significantly less informative and trustworthy compared to Types A and C, whereas conventional content (Type-A) was overall perceived as significantly more effective than Type-B. Type-C (combination) content was considered as equally humorous to Type-B, but also equally informative and effective compared to Type-A content (Fig. 2).

4. Associations between variables. The most prominent associations revealed by chi-square testing included: (a) concern about FS issues with Type-B content considered as informative; (b) age group with sharing likelihood of Type-C content; (c) level of familiarization on FS and MBs issues with likelihood of “liking” and sharing some or all three content types; (d) highest level of studies and academic/professional discipline, with “liking” of Type-A and C contents.

Post hoc tests examined the exact sources of dependencies. Regarding the association of “FS issues concern” with Type-B content (humorous) considered as awareness-raising, highly-concerned people strongly agreed on this content’s informative nature, whereas those declaring limited FS concern disagreed

Fig. 2. Kruskal-Wallis H-test of effectiveness-related variables across content types: (A) Informative/Educational/Creating awareness; (B) Perceived effectiveness.

with this characterization. MBs experts were significantly more likely to “like” Type-A and B contents and share all three types, compared to less FS-familiarized participants who were very unlikely to “like” or share Type-A or C contents, while significantly less of the MB-unfamiliarized people would share any of all three content types on SM. Respondents of an Environment/Fisheries background were significantly more likely to “like” Type-A content, while Type-C content was significantly more “likeable” by participants within Veterinary Medicine and Chemistry/Pharmacology sectors. By contrast, people of ICT/Social sciences’ backgrounds were greatly unlikely to “like” Type-A and C contents compared to other disciplines.

Overall, it was concluded that the majority of the participants perceived SM materials entailing humorous elements (Type B) as less effective than conventional, purely informative posts, although the former were more likely to be “liked” or shared by SM-users affiliated or familiarized with the FS and MB fields. In addition, combination content comprising humorous MB-related images supplemented by scientific explanatory text

in a video format (Type C), was not perceived as significantly less effective compared to conventional. Finally, considering the drawback that humor use in RC is frequently criticized for trivializing risks' importance, the above evidence favors the potential usability of combined content types for RC purposes through SM in FS/MB, and possibly in other closely-related sectors.

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